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Keywords: Agricultural residues, Autohydrolysis, Membrane technology, Prebiotic, Xylooligosaccharides, Structural characterization

Vine shoots as new source for the manufacture of prebiotic oligosaccharides

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Abstract

Vine shoots were subjected to a hydrothermal treatment to cause the selective solubilisation of the hemicelluloses. The hemicelluloses solubilisation products were refined by a sequential processing with nanofiltration and ion exchange obtaining a refined product with a purity of 99%. A depth chemical and structural characterization of the purified oligosaccharide mixture from vine shoots was performed for the first time by HPLC, FTIR, HPAEC-PAD, MALDI-TOF and UPLC-ESI-MS. The characterization showed the presence of oligosaccharide mixture with a wide polymerization degree (DP=2-17) and a rich substitution pattern. Moreover, the thermal behaviour of the mixture was evaluated by TGA in order to obtain information about the thermal and storage conditions during its incorporation into processed functional foods. The thermal and acid stability of the obtained oligosaccharides was also evaluated corroborating their resistance to the digestive conditions. The assessment of the prebiotic activity of the digested mixture was carried out by *in vitro* fermentability with faecal inocula from human volunteers by the monitoring of short chain fatty acids production and the population dynamic of bifidobacteria by FISH.

Keywords: agricultural residues, autohydrolysis, membrane technology, prebiotic, xylooligosaccharides, structural characterization

1. Introduction

The interest in prebiotic oligosaccharides as functional ingredients has gained attention due to their ability to benefit the humans' health. Prebiotics are described as "selectively fermented ingredients that allow specific changes, both in the composition and/or activity of the gut microbiota, conferring benefits to the host's wellbeing and health" (Roberfroid, 2007). Prebiotics pass through the stomach and small bowel intact, and once they reach the large bowel they are fermented by microbiota such as bifidobacteria and lactobacilli, generating short chain fatty acids (SCFA) such as propionate, butyrate or acetate (Gullón et al., 2010). Many important physiological events such as the bowel functions, calcium absorption, lipid metabolism or the reduction of the risk of colon cancer between others have been related to SCFA (Rycroft, Jones, Gibson, & Rastall, 2001). Apart from these benefits, prebiotics have been reported to improve the inhibition of pathogenic bacteria, the prevention of infections and allergies or the regulation of the lipid and glucose metabolism (Gullón, Gullón, Tavaría, Alonso & Pintado, 2015; Gullón, Pintado et al., 2015).

The properties shown by the prebiotics make them suitable for elderly people as it has been reported that there is a correlation between the age, the chronic diseases, the changes in the composition of the intestinal microbiota, and the host's immune system (Rowland & Gill, 2008). It has been observed that the composition of the microbiota changes with the age, being it possibly influenced by the medication, the gastrointestinal infections or by the diet (Gómez, Veiga, Parajó, & Alonso, 2015). These changes could increase the susceptibility to diseases such as gastroenteritis or infections of *Clostridium difficile*, being the intake of prebiotics a kind of prevention against them (Woodmansey, McMurdo, Macfarlane, & Macfarlane, 2004). Nowadays inulin, lactulose, galactooligosaccharides (GalOS) and fructooligosaccharides (FOS) are commercialised as prebiotics as there is enough scientific evidences about them (Gómez et al., 2015). However, there are other food ingredients as fructans, galactans, xylooligosaccharides, β -glucans, or arabinoxylans which are gaining attention due to their prebiotic properties (Cummings, Macfarlane, & Englyst, 2001; Mei, Carey, Tosh, & Kostrynska, 2011).

Xylooligosaccharides are receiving more attention in the recent years. These oligomers are formed by xylose units linked through β -1,4 glycosidic bonds and they could present arabinosyl, acetyl, uronic or phenolic groups as substituents (Gullón et al. 2010). These oligosaccharides can be obtained from different lignocellulosic residues such as hardwoods, hulls, brans, corn cobs, corn stover or from industrial by-products like brewery spent grains and shells (Gullón et al. 2010). The low cost, the renewability and the high availability of this feedstock make them a promising source for the obtaining of xylooligosaccharides. The feedstock together with the

conditions employed for the obtaining of oligosaccharides influence both their substituents and their polymerization degree, being these two factors which provide different prebiotic activities to the oligosaccharide (Gullón, Gullón, Moure, Domínguez, & Parajó, 2009). Between the different type of treatments used to obtain oligosaccharides from lignocellulosic residues the following ones could be found; enzymatic hydrolysis, steam explosion, hydrothermal, dilute acid treatment or a combination of these processes (Chen, Swanson et al., 2016; Chen, Wang et al., 2016).

In the present work, the prebiotic activity of oligosaccharides obtained from vine shoots was evaluated, as this feedstock has not been used for the production of prebiotics as far as we know. The vine shoots is one of the most abundant winery residue, being 2-4 tons of it produced per hectare and per year (Nabais, Laginhas, Carrot, & Carrot, 2010). However, this residue has not been completely exploited yet as it is mainly used for the obtaining of energy.

From the different possible methods for the obtaining of oligosaccharides the hydrothermal treatment was chosen for this work, as it is an environmentally friendly process, as no chemicals are used and the obtained products are appropriate for the food industry. Dávila, Gordobil, Labidi and Gullón, (2016) observed that the hydrothermal process of the vine shoots permitted the conversion of the 83.1% of the xylan present in the raw material, which was the main constituent of its hemicellulosic fraction, into substituted xylooligosaccharides.

However, during the hydrothermal treatments apart from the oligosaccharides, monosaccharides and non-saccharide compounds are also liberated, making it necessary a purification step of the obtained liquor prior to the employment of the oligosaccharides in the food industry. Between the non-saccharide compounds, extractives, acid-soluble lignin and inorganic compounds could be present in the liquors as simultaneously to the hydrolysis of hemicelluloses the solubilisation of these compounds could take place (Vegas, Alonso, Domínguez, & Parajó, 2005). The purification of the hydrothermally obtained liquors could be carried out by different technologies such as the liquid-liquid extraction, the membrane filtration or the ion exchange (Gómez et al. 2015). Gullón, Eibes, Dávila et al. (2017), Gullón, Eibes, Moreira et al. (2017) carried out the purification of the liquors obtained in the hydrothermal treatment of vine shoots by a liquid-liquid extraction, observing that the impurities were reduced from 2.13 Kg/100Kg dry vine shoots to 0.98 Kg/100Kg dry vine shoots after the purification of the liquors obtained at 200 °C. However, in this work, the purification of the liquors obtained by the hydrothermal treatment of the vine shoots at 200°C was carried out by membrane filtration, using nanofiltration. The employment of nanofiltration would permit the concentration of the liquors removing compounds with low molar mass such as the monosaccharides or phenolic compounds (Gullón, González-Muñoz, Domínguez, & Parajó, 2008).

The aim of this work was to refine the liquors obtained by the hydrothermal treatment of the vine shoots using sequential steps of membrane technology in concentration and discontinuous diafiltration-concentration mode followed by an ion exchange process. The purified oligosaccharides were characterized by HPLC, HPAEC-PAD, FTIR, TGA, MALDI-TOF and UPLC-DADMS-ESI. The thermal and acid stability of the obtained oligosaccharides was also evaluated simulating the conditions that the oligosaccharides would suffer during their digestion once they are used as food functional ingredients. The assessment of the prebiotic effect of the refined oligosaccharides was carried out through anaerobic fermentation using fecal inocula and mimicking the gut intestinal conditions. The monitoring of the fermentation progress was performed by analysing the production of Short Chain Fatty Acids (SCFA, i.e., acetate, propionate and butyrate) as well as other minor acids and measuring the consumption of oligosaccharides. The bifidobacterial growth was evaluated by FISH.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Feedstock

Vine shoots from the grape variety Hondarribi Zuri were obtained from the pruning of the vine after the vintage of 2015 and they were supplied by the local winery Aldakoa S.L. (Basque Country, Spain). Once collected the vine shoots were milled and sieved in order to have a single and homogenized lot with a particle size smaller than 0.4 mm. This lot was stored in a dark and dry place until it was used. The composition of this raw material has been reported in previous works (Dávila et al., 2016).

2.2. Hydrothermal treatment of the vine shoots

The vine shoots were subjected to a hydrothermal treatment by mixing them with water in a liquid to solid ratio of 8 kg/kg (oven-dried basis) in a 1.5 L stainless steel Parr reactor. The treatment was carried out at 200 °C in a non-isothermal regimen being the temperature controlled by a Parr PID control. Once cooled down the solid and the liquid fractions were separated by filtration. The liquors were stored at -18°C until their further use.

2.3. Manufacture of refined oligosaccharides by nanofiltration and ion exchange

The liquors obtained in the autohydrolysis treatment were processed following the sequence shown in the Fig. 1. The membrane processing was carried out using a EMD Millipore™ Amicon™ Bioseparations Stirred Cell (EMD Millipore, St Charles, MO, USA) provided with a 1 kDa cut off regenerated cellulose membrane with an effective membrane area of $45.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$. The pressure in the device was generated using a compressed nitrogen gas cylinder, and it was controlled by a regulator, whereas a gauge attached to the inlet line was used to measure it. The

liquors were continuously stirred with a magnetic stirrer bar and the stirring rate was maintained constant to avoid the formation of a deep vortex.

During the concentration stage, the autohydrolysis liquors (stream A) were subjected to a dead-end filtration using the described device until a Volume Concentration Ratio (VCR) of 3.3 was achieved. The resulting retentate (stream B in Fig. 1) was subjected to discontinuous diafiltration-concentration through the same membrane using 3 diavolumes (defined as the volume ratio between the added water and the initial solution) and the diluted sample was concentrated up to a VCR=5.1 yielding the stream D, as it can be seen in Fig. 1. The operations were performed at room temperature and a transmembrane pressure of 4 bar, since in preliminary assays (data not shown) it was observed that these conditions permitted the highest oligosaccharide retention. The stream D obtained during the membrane processing was further purified by ion exchange using an IRA-96 resin (from Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). The solution and the resin were maintained in contact overnight with gentle agitation at room temperature using a mass ratio of 15:1 (g/g). The resulting solution (the stream F in the Fig. 1) was subjected to a compositional analysis and then, it was freeze-dried (stream G in the Fig. 1) to evaluate its potential prebiotic activity. The composition of streams A, B, D and F/G were analyzed as it is indicated below.

Fig. 1. Refining processing of autohydrolysis liquors from vine shoots

2.4. Characterization of purified hemicelluloses derived saccharides

2.4.1. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

The streams A, B, D and F/G of the Fig. 1 were analysed as it was described by Rivas, Santos, and Parajó, (2017) and Gullón et al (2014). Briefly, the samples were subjected to the quantification of glucose, xylose, arabinose, acetic acid, galacturonic acid, furfural and hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) using a HPLC 1200 series instrument (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with a refraction index (RI) and an Ultraviolet-Diode Array (UV-DAD) detector using an Aminex HPX-87H column (from BioRad Life Science Group Hercules, CA, USA). The determination of mannose and galactose were performed using a CARBOSep CHO-682 column (from Transgenomic Inc., Omaha, NE 68164, USA).

The quantification of the oligosaccharides and the quantification of the acetyl and galacturonyl groups bind to them was carried out taking into account the increase observed in the concentration of monosaccharides, acetic acid and galacturonic acid after subjecting the different streams to a quantitative posthydrolysis (4% H₂SO₄ for 30 min, 121 °C). The samples obtained after the quantitative acid hydrolysis were analyzed by HPLC as described above. The content of non-volatile compounds (NVC) in the liquors was measured by oven-drying them at 105 °C until they present a constant weight. All analyses were made in triplicate.

2.4.2. Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionisation Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF)

The stream G was analysed by MALDI-TOF-MS using an Ultraflex workstation (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) in positive ion mode following the method described by Gullón et al. (2014). The calibration was performed with xylooligosaccharides with a polymerization degree (DP) between 2 and 6 supplied by Megazyme.

2.4.3. High performance anion exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC-PAD)

The refined hemicellulosic oligosaccharides (stream G) were analysed by HPAEC-PAD using an ICS3000 instrument (Dionex, Sunnyvale, USA) equipped with a 250 ×2 mm CarboPac PA-1 column in combination with a 25 ×2 mm CarboPac PA guard column (from Dionex). Xylooligosaccharides with DP from 2 to 6 provided by Megazyme were used as calibration standards.

2.4.4. Attenuated total reflection - fourier transformed infrared radiation (FTIR)

The FTIR analysis of the refined hemicellulosic oligosaccharides (stream G) was performed on a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer. The equipment was working in transmission mode with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and accumulating a total of 8 scans. The spectrum was obtained from a range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

2.4.5. Ultraperformance liquid chromatography-diode array detector-electrospray ionization-mass spectrometry (UPLC-DAD-ESI-MS)

The UPLC-DAD-ESI-MS analysis of the oligosaccharides present in the G stream was performed using an UPLC (Acquity, Waters) equipped with a diode array detector. The sample was dissolved in methanol achieving approx. 500 mg/L and $5\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of it were injected in the UPLC system. The separation was carried out at 40°C using a C18 analytical column (Acquity, $100\text{ mm} \times 2.1\text{ mm}$, $1.7\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particle size). The mobile phases used were acidified water (0.1% formic acid, v/v) (phase A) and methanol (phase B). The sample was eluted using the following elution gradient at a constant flow rate of 0.3 mL/min : 0 min 99% A until 2 min, 2 min 99% B until 26 min, 26 min 1% A until 27.5 min; 28 min 99% A until 30 min. The UV spectrum was recorded from 200 to 500 nm, whereas the chromatograms were registered at 254, 280, and 320 nm. A LCT Premier XE (Waters) fitted with an electrospray ionization (ESI) interface was used for the mass spectrometry analysis. These analyses were performed using scans from m/z 100 to 2000. Capillary voltage and cone voltage were set at 2000 and 100 V, respectively, in positive ionization mode.

2.4.6. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The freeze-dried oligosaccharides (Stream G) were subjected to a thermogravimetric analysis using a TGA/SDTA RSI analyzer 851 Mettler Toledo. Between 3 and 5 mg of the sample were tested from 25°C to 600°C under a nitrogen atmosphere using a heating rate of 10°C/min .

2.4.7. Simulated *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion

The purified oligosaccharides (stream G in Figure 1), previously freeze-dried, were subjected to a process of *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion according to the protocol described by Gullón, Gullón et al. (2015); Gullón, Pintado et al. (2015). The method consists in simulating the three stages of the digestion: the mouth phase, the gastric digestion and the small intestine conditions. The mouth phase was simulated using salivary α -amylase (to pH 7.0) for 5 min, while the gastric digestion was performed by acidifying the solution to pH 2 and by adding pepsin for 2 h. The conditions of the small intestine were simulated using pancreatin and bovine bile salts at pH 7 for 2 h. The solutions of each stage were incubated in a shaking water bath at 37°C and 50

rpm. At the end of the incubation period, the sample was heated at 100 °C for 5 min to inactivate the enzymes. Then, the solution was transferred to a dialysis membrane of 1 kDa molecular weight cut-off and dialyzed overnight at 25°C in a solution of NaCl (10 mM) to remove the low molecular weight digestion products. The digested oligosaccharides were analyzed by HPLC and HPAEC-PAD (as described above) to verify that the digestion conditions did not modify the chemical nor the structural composition. The digested sample was freeze-dried for the subsequent *in vitro* colonic fermentation experiments.

2.4.8. Prebiotic effect

The evaluation of the prebiotic effect of the purified XOS was conducted according to the procedure described by Gullón et al. (2014). The concentration of the digested sample (XOS) and FOS (used for comparative purposes) in the fermentation medium were 10 g/L. Faecal samples were obtained from three healthy human volunteers, who did not consume antibiotics or probiotics, and who did not have any digestive diseases during the three months previous to the study.

All the additions and inoculations were carried out inside an anaerobic cabinet (5% H₂, 10% CO₂ and 85% N₂). The fermentation was carried out at 37°C for 48 h without shaking. At selected fermentation times (0, 4, 10, 24 and 48 h) samples from the media were taken and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 min. The supernatants were filtered for a subsequent HPLC analysis of the SCFA and lactate and to determine the consumption of oligosaccharides. The pellets were analysed for quantification of bifidobacteria by fluorescent *in situ* hybridization (FISH) following the methodology described in Gullón et al. (2011), 2014).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Unrefined hemicelluloses solubilization products from vine shoots: characterization

The hydrothermal treatment of vine shoots, a feedstock rich in xylan, causes the breakdown of its chains leading xylooligosaccharides with substituents. Nevertheless, apart from the solubilisation of the hemicellulosic fraction, other collateral processes could take place during the hydrothermal treatment, such as the removal of extractives, the solubilisation of acid-soluble lignin and inorganic compounds or the generation of degradation products from carbohydrates. Therefore, to obtain a dissolution enriched in XOS with a high purity is necessary to submit the autohydrolysis liquors to refining stages.

The data of the optimization of the hydrothermal treatment conditions and the conversion of the hemicelluloses of the vine shoots have been given in a previous work (Gullón, Eibes, Dávila et al., 2017; Gullón, Eibes, Moreira et al., 2017). The composition of the crude autohydrolysis

liquors is collected in Table 1 (Stream A in the Fig 1). As it can be seen in Table 1, the liquors were made up of water, non-volatile compounds (NVC, i.e., XOS, glucooligosaccharides (GOS), galactosyl, manosyl, acetyl and galacturonyl substituents of the XOS, and monosaccharides such as glucose, xylose and arabinose). They also contained volatile compounds (VC, i.e., acetic acid) and other non-volatile compounds (ONVC, integrated among other, by inorganic compounds, extractives and lignin-derived products). The amount of the total oligosaccharides, being them the target product of this study, was 0.589 kg/kg NVC (considered as the joint contribution of XOS, GOS, GalOS, ManOS, AcOS and galacturonyl substituents), the amount of total monosaccharides achieved was 0.0896 kg/kg NVC and the ONVC accounted a mass fraction of 0.321 kg/kg NVC. With the aim of obtaining food-grade oligosaccharides, the crude liquors were submitted to refining stages, which could be a challenge due to the heterogeneous composition of the autohydrolysis liquors. In order to achieve this purpose, several conventional methods of separation have been assayed (Gullón et al., 2008), being the refining treatment chosen in this work the membrane processing which is an emerging technology with high potential for the purification of this type of dissolutions (Gullón et al., 2010).

Table 1. Composition of the streams A, B, D and F/G (see Fig. 1)

Component ^a	Stream			
	A	B	D	F/G
Glucose	0.004	0.001	0.000	0.003
Xylose	0.041	0.013	0.006	0.008
Arabinose	0.045	0.001	0.000	0.001
Glucooligosaccharides	0.106	0.157	0.170	0.194
Xylooligosaccharides	0.367	0.479	0.514	0.571
Arabinosyl substituents	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.004
Galactosyl substituent	0.011	0.012	0.013	0.020
Manosyl substituents	0.020	0.022	0.023	0.036
Acetyl groups	0.048	0.078	0.097	0.100
Galacturonyl substituents	0.036	0.041	0.044	0.052
ONVC ^b	0.321	0.194	0.130	0.009
NVC ^c	0.026	0.077	0.044	0.041
VC ^d (acetic acid)	0.117	0.038	0.016	0.014

^aExpressed as kg of component/ kg of non volatile compound (NVC). ^bONVC, other non volatile compounds. ^cNVC, non volatile compounds. ^dVC, volatile compound

3.2. Refining of the hemicelluloses solubilisation products from vine shoots

The liquors obtained from the autohydrolysis treatment of the vine shoots were purified by sequential stages of nanofiltration operating in concentration and discontinuous diafiltration-concentration mode followed by an ion exchange process as it can be seen in the Fig. 1. The compositional data of the streams obtained in each of the stages of the refining process (Streams A, B, D and F/G) are collected in the Table 1.

During the first stage, the stream A was processed by nano-filtration using a membrane of a molecular weight cut-off of 1 kDa and operating on concentration mode until a VCR of 3.3 was achieved yielding the corresponding retentate (Stream B) and permeate (stream C). From the corresponding mass balance, it can be inferred that the percentages of recovery of the NVC in stream B with respect to stream A were in the range of 2.0% to 20.7% for the monosaccharides and 20.9% for the acetic acid. The recovery yields for the oligosaccharides were 95.6% for GOS, 84.2% for XOS, 71.5% for GalOS and for ManOS, 100% for the acetyl groups and 71.5% for galacturonyl substituents. During this stage, a high percentage of the monosaccharides together with the removal of 61.1% of the ONVC present in the liquors was achieved (reducing it from 0.321 kg/kg NVC to 0.194 kg/kg NVC) leading to an increase of the mass fraction of the total oligosaccharides from 0.589 kg/kg NVC to 0.790 kg/kg NVC.

The second stage consisted on a discontinuous diafiltration (DD) and concentration mode and it was carried out to increase the purity of the oligosaccharides contained in the stream B. In this stage the stream B was diluted with distilled water three times (diavolume (DV) = 3) and then concentrated until a VCR = 5.1, which led to Stream D and the Stream E. From the corresponding mass balances, it can be estimated that the removal percentage of ONVC in the stream D with respect to the stream B was 61.8%, which supposed a reduction of its mass fraction from 0.194 kg/kg NVC to 0.130 kg/kg NVC. Regarding the target compounds of this study, the recovery yields on the stream D with respect to the stream B was a 61.03% for GOS, 60.82% for XOS, 60.82% for GalOS and ManOS, 69.96% for AcOS and 60.82% for galacturonyl substituents. This stage allowed the removal of 73-81.1% of the monosaccharides of the stream B and 75.4% of the acetic acid. Taking into account the overall mass balance of the concentration-DD-concentration processing the 85.2% of the ONVC of the stream A were removed. The recovery percentages on stream D with respect to the stream A were 0.5-5.4% for monosaccharides, 5.1% for acetic acid, while for the oligosaccharides these percentages were pretty higher (58.3% for GOS, 51.2% XOS, 43.5% for GalOS and ManOS, 73.4% for AcOS and 46.8% for galacturonyl substituents).

The stream D was subjected to a subsequent stage of ion exchange using an anionic resin (Amberlite IRA 96) to remove the remaining ONVC yielding the stream F in Fig. 1. During this stage a 92.97% of the ONVC were removed from the stream D resulting in a decrease of its mass fraction from 0.130 kg/kg NVC to 0.011 kg/kg NVC. After the ion exchange process all the monosaccharides present in the stream D were recovered while only a 67.6% of the acetic acid was recovered. In the case of the target compounds, the recovery percentages on stream F with respect to stream D were 90.9% for GOS, 88.5% for XOS, 100% for GalOS and ManOS, 82.6% for AcOS and 94.4% for galacturonyl substituents.

Considering the whole concentration-DD-concentration and ion exchange sequence the mass fraction of the total oligosaccharides increased from 0.589 kg/kg NVC to 0.977 kg/kg NVC confirming that almost all the non-saccharide compounds of the crude liquor were removed during the refining stages yielding a refined liquor.

These data show the suitability of the refining scheme to remove the ONVC (global removal 98.96%) and the monosaccharides (closely 100%) with global recovery percentages of 53.0% for GOS, of 45.3% for XOS, of 43.5% GalOS, of 43.5% for ManOS, of 57.8% for AcOS and of 41.05% for galacturonyl substituents. Thus, the proposed purification scheme permitted the obtaining of a stream enriched in oligosaccharides with high purity which could present bioactive properties. The data obtained in this work are in agreement with the ones reported by Rivas et al. (2017) who achieved an almost total removal of ONVC from the autohydrolysis liquors obtained from birch wood employing a similar scheme to the one proposed in the present work. Buruaina, Gómez, Vizireanu, and Garrote, (2017) obtained xylooligosaccharides from corn stover with a purity slightly lower than the one obtained in this work (89% *versus* 99%) working with a nanofiltration system followed by a cation or anion exchange step.

3.3. Structural characterization of refined oligosaccharide mixture

The biological properties of the hemicellulose-derived products depend on their molecular weight distribution as well as on their substitution degree. Taking this into account a deeper structural characterization of the freeze-fried refined mixture (stream G) was performed using complementary techniques such as FTIR, HPAEC-PAD, MALDI-TOF, TGA and UPLC-DAD-ESI-MS. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that a detailed description of the structure of the refined oligosaccharides from vine shoots obtained by autohydrolysis is reported.

The FTIR spectroscopy was used not only to determine the type of functional groups present in the refined oligosaccharides but also to check their purity, to determine their structure, and to elucidate complexing and inter-molecular interactions (Fang, Sun, & Tomkinson, 2000). The FTIR of the freeze-dried oligosaccharides (stream G in the Fig. 1) was carried out, being its spectra plotted in the Fig. 2. This spectrum shows the typical transmittance bands expected for hemicellulosic oligosaccharides and the peak assignation was carried out taking into account what has been reported in literature. The region between 1148 and 924 cm^{-1} corresponds to the fingerprint of xylans. The maximum band observed at 1042 cm^{-1} is attributed to the C-O and C-C stretching or to the C-OH bending and to the glycosidic C-O-C, indicating the predominance of xylan oligosaccharides (Fang et al., 2000). This also could indicate that the oligosaccharides present in the stream G present a very low degree of branching, which is sustained by the results obtained from the chemical analysis of the stream G. The small band observed at 903 cm^{-1} could

correspond to C₁ group frequency or to the ring frequency, suggesting the presence of β-glycosidic linkages between the xylopiranoses units of the main xylan chain (Chen, Swanson et al., 2016; Chen, Wang et al., 2016). The signal observed at 1150 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of arabinosyl side chains and the band observed at 1076 cm⁻¹ indicated the glycosidic bond vibrations of arabinoxylans (Dávila et al., 2016). According to what Gullón et al. (2011) reported the acetyl groups gave weak absorption bands at 1732, 1379 and 1251 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the C=O stretching, to the symmetric CH₃ bending and to the single bonded oxygen (C-O) stretching vibrations.

The methylglucuronosyl residues are present in their ionised form, which is confirmed by the asymmetric and symmetric (C=O) stretching vibrations of the carboxylate group at 1601 cm⁻¹ and 1420 cm⁻¹, respectively.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of the refined oligosaccharides of the stream G

The HPAEC-PAD elution profile of the stream G is shown in the Fig. 3. It corroborates the presence of mostly linear oligomers with a DP up to 6, and oligomers with DP > 6 as well as more complex substituted oligomers. Gullón et al. (2011) reported that the acetylated oligomers could not be observed with HPAEC, due to the saponification of the sample during its elution with a highly alkaline solution.

Fig. 3. HPAEC-PAD elution profile for stream G

The refined oligosaccharide mixture was also analysed by MALDI-TOF-MS to obtain more detailed information about the structure of the purified oligosaccharides. The Table 2 shows the attribution of the mass signals of the MALDI-TOF-MS spectra to specific oligosaccharides, which were detected as sodium or potassium adducts. The predominant oligosaccharides corresponded to chains of pentoses highly substituted by acetyl and methylglucuronosyl groups and with a DP ranging from 3 to 18. Other oligosaccharide sequences containing both pentoses and hexoses were also identified in the spectrum. Overall, the complex chemical structure observed for the oligosaccharides obtained from the vine shoots is similar to what it has been published for other oligomeric compounds obtained by autohydrolysis from different feedstocks (Buruiana et al., 2017; Gullón et al., 2018; Ho, Kosik, Lovegrove, Charalampopoulos, & Rastall, 2018; Rico, Gullón, Alonso, Parajó, & Yáñez, 2018).

The stream G was also analyzed by UPLC electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (UPLC-DAD-ESI-MS) in positive ion mode. Five peaks were eluted (Fig. 4) and the oligosaccharides were tentatively identified ions in the ESI-MS spectra which are collected in Table 3. The following ion oligosaccharides series were tentatively identified: peak 1 corresponded to $[\text{Pent}_n\text{Ac}_m\text{Na}]^+$ series where $n=3, 4, 5, 6, 8$ and 9 , $m=2, 4$ and 5 and the peak 2 was constituted by $[\text{Pent}_n\text{Ur}_x\text{MeUr}]$ series where $n=2, 3, 5$ and 8 , $x=1$ and 3 . $[\text{Pent}_n\text{Hex}_2\text{Ac}_m]$ series where $n=2, 3, 5$, and 7 , $m=1$ and 2 were present in peak 3, while the peak 4 was formed by $[\text{Pent}_n\text{Hex}_2\text{Ac}_m]$ series $n=1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7$ and 9 , $m=1$ and 2 . The peak 5 corresponded to $[\text{Pent}_n\text{Hex}_2\text{Ac}_m]$ series where $n=2, 3, 5, 6$, and 7 , $m=4, 5$ and 6 . These data confirm those obtained by MALDI-TOF and are in agreement with the ones reported in the literature in matter of structural

characterization of substituted oligosaccharides from lignocellulosic materials (Coelho, Rocha, Moreira, Domingues, & Coimbra, 2016).

Previous studies about the biological properties of the XOS has reported that mixtures of XOS with a wide range of DP and a rich substitution pattern had better bifidogenic properties than the linear XOS (Moura et al., 2008). Based on the structural characteristics identified by MALDI-TOF-MS and UPLC-DAD-ESI-MS, it could be suggested that the XOS obtained in this study would have a potential application as prebiotic agents.

Table 2. MALDI-TOF results and structural attribution of Stream G in Fig. 1.

m/z	Structure	m/z	Structure
702.3	Pent ₅ Na	1255.0	Pent ₃ Hex ₃ MeUrAc ₃ K
723.8	PentHex ₂ Ac ₅ K	1297.6	Pent ₇ Ac ₃ MeUrK
771.5	Pent ₂ Hex ₂ Ac ₃ K	1340.5	Pent ₆ Hex ₂ Ac ₄ K
861.6	Pent ₃ Hex ₂ Ac ₂ K	1369.8	Pent ₉ Ac ₃ MeNa
885.4	Pent ₅ Ac ₄ K	1385.6	Pent ₈ HexAc ₃ Na
903.8	Pent ₃ Hex ₂ Ac ₃ K	1428.7	Pent ₈ Ac ₃ MeUrK
949.0	Pent ₄ MeUr ₂ Na	1471.2	Pent ₈ Ac ₄ MeUrK
992.8	Pent ₄ Hex ₂ Ac ₂ K	1530.4	Pent ₉ Ac ₃ UrNa
1008.3	Pent ₇ AcNa	1690.9	Pent ₁₀ HexAc ₄ Na
1035.0	Pent ₄ Hex ₂ Ac ₃ K	1705.1	Pent ₁₀ Ac ₄ UrNa
1048.3	Pent ₇ Ac ₂ Na	1775.4	Pent ₇ Hex ₅ Na
1124.4	Pent ₅ Hex ₂ Ac ₂ K	1865.7	Pent ₄ Hex ₈ Na
1166.8	Pent ₅ Hex ₂ Ac ₃ K	2173.8	Pent ₈ Hex ₃ Ac ₅ MeUr ₂ Na
1182.3	Pent ₈ Ac ₂ Na	2337.3	Pent ₁₆ Ac ₄ K
1209.3	Pent ₅ Hex ₂ Ac ₄ K	2349.9	PentHex ₁₂ AcMeUrNa
1224.6	Pent ₇ Ac ₂ UrNa	2653.9	Pent ₁₇ HexMeUrK

MALDI-TOF spectrum of stream G (Pent=pentose; Hex=hexose; Ac=Acetyl group; Ur= uronic acid; Me= methyl)

Fig. 4. UV (254 nm) and MS (positive ionization) chromatograms of stream G.

The assessment of the thermal stability of the stream G was carried out by a thermogravimetric analysis, being the corresponding thermogravimetric curve and the first derivative curves shown in the Fig. 5. Taking into account that these bioactive compounds have important applications in the food sector, due to their prebiotic and antioxidant properties, their thermal analysis provides relevant information about the thermal and storage conditions of these compounds during their incorporation into processed functional foods.

As it can be seen in Fig. 5, the thermal degradation of the refined oligosaccharides could be divided in four weight loss phases. During the first stage, which took place in the interval 50-150°C a weight loss of around 4% was observed associated to the water evaporation process. The second degradation stage occurred between 150 and 250°C, being observed at 218°C its maximum degradation temperature (T_{max}). In this stage, a weight loss of around 20% was observed probably due to the degradation of low molecular weight oligosaccharides present in the sample and to the removal of the branches from the main chain, which are easily cleaved from the backbone (Chen, Swanson et al., 2016; Chen, Wang et al., 2016; Yang, Song, Yuan, Xu & Sun, 2011). The third degradation stage observed between 250-325°C with a T_{max} of 309.5°C, in which around a 40% of the mass of the sample was lost, it could correspond to the rapid thermal degradation of the hemicelluloses backbone due to the cleavage of the β -(1 → 6)- and (1 → 4)-glucosidic linkages (Chen, Swanson et al., 2016; Chen, Wang et al., 2016). The last degradation stage took place between 350 and 600 °C which could be attributed to decomposition of the residue into gaseous products as CO, CO₂, CH₄, CH₃COOH or HCOOH between others (Wang et al., 2016). At 600°C 22.83% of the sample remained as char which is lower than what Dávila et al. (2016) reported for the oligosaccharides obtained by autohydrolysis of vine shoots at different severities. This can indicate the presence of remaining impurities in the oligosaccharides.

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetric curve (TGA) and first derivative (DTG) curves of stream G.

Table 3. Tentative oligosaccharides series identified as [M+Na⁺] ions in the ESI-MS spectra of the peaks eluted from stream G by UPLC.

Peak #	m/z	Oligosaccharides series	Peak #	m/z	Oligosaccharides series	Peak #	m/z	Oligosaccharides series	Peak #	m/z	Oligosaccharides series	Peak #	m/z	Oligosaccharides series
1	520.94	[Pent ₃ Ac ₂ Na] ⁺	2	647.98	[Pent ₂ UrMeUr]	3	647.98	[Pent ₂ Hex ₂ Ac]	4	515.99	[PentHex ₂ Ac]	5	773.97	[Pent ₂ Hex ₂ Ac ₄]
	737.97	[Pent ₄ Ac ₄ Na] ⁺		779.97	[Pent ₃ UrMeUr]		779.98	[Pent ₃ Hex ₂ Ac]		821.97	[Pent ₃ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]		905.97	[Pent ₃ Hex ₂ Ac ₄]
	869.97	[Pent ₅ Ac ₄ Na] ⁺		1133.96	[Pent ₃ Ur ₃ MeUr2H] ⁺		911.97	[Pent ₄ Hex ₂ Ac]		953.97	[Pent ₄ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]		1211.96	[Pent ₅ Hex ₂ Ac ₅]
	1001.97	[Pent ₆ Ac ₄ Na] ⁺		1398.98	[Pent ₅ Ur ₃ MeUr3H] ⁺		1043.96	[Pent ₅ Hex ₂ Ac]		1085.96	[Pent ₅ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]		1343.95	[Pent ₆ Hex ₂ Ac ₅]
	1265.96	[Pent ₈ Ac ₄ Na] ⁺		1818.84	[Pent ₈ Ur ₃ MeUr3H ⁺ Na ⁺]		1349.94	[Pent ₇ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]		1217.95	[Pent ₆ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]		1475.95	[Pent ₇ Hex ₂ Ac ₅]
	1440.95	[Pent ₉ Ac ₅ Na] ⁺								1349.95	[Pent ₇ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]		1517.96	[Pent ₇ Hex ₂ Ac ₆]
										1613.93	[Pent ₉ Hex ₂ Ac ₂]			

Pentose (Pent), Hex (Hexose), MeUr (Methyluronic acid), Ur (Uronic acid), Ac (Acetyl group)

3.4. Assessment of the Prebiotic Potential of the refined oligosaccharide mixture

3.4.1. Simulation of the gastrointestinal digestion

One of the requirements that oligosaccharides must meet to be considered as prebiotics is their ability to resist the process of the gastrointestinal digestion (Gibson et al., 2017). For this purpose, the refined oligosaccharides (stream G) were subjected to conditions that simulate the acidic gastric environment by using salivary α -amylase, gastric pepsin, and trypsin under pH conditions of 7, 2, and 7, respectively. The results obtained from HPLC and HPAEC-PAD revealed that oligosaccharides obtained from the vine shoots by a hydrothermal treatment were resistant to the gastrointestinal digestion, since no significant changes were observed in their molecular weight distribution or in the release of monosaccharides (data not shown). Similar conclusions were also observed by Sánchez et al. (2009) when they evaluated the stability of different arabinoxylan-oligosaccharides simulating the stomach and small intestine conditions.

3.4.2. Impact of the refined oligosaccharides on the organic acids profile during the fermentation

After the gastrointestinal digestion stage, the sample was evaluated by *in vitro* fermentation with human faecal microbiota to confirm its prebiotic potential. The data concerning to the lactate and SCFA production and the pH variations during the *in vitro* faecal fermentations, are displayed in the Table 4.

Both FOS and the digested oligosaccharides were metabolized by the intestinal microbiota leading to a production of organic acids and to a pH drop of 2.7 and 2.4 units when the FOS and the digested oligosaccharides was employed, respectively. The total concentration of SCFAs produced by the 48 h fermentation of the digested oligosaccharides was considerably higher ($p \leq 0.05$) than the one observed for FOS, with values of 139.4 and 102.6 mM, respectively. Low production of SCFAs was obtained when a medium without carbon source was used, as a result of protein or amino acid fermentation by putrefactive bacteria.

For both FOS and refined oligosaccharides, the acetate was the main metabolic product, which accounted for about 60% of the total SCFAs, followed by propionate, butyrate, formiate and lactate. A low lactate production was observed at short fermentation times, being more abundant in the experiments containing FOS (9.33 *versus* 4.50 mM). Lactate is a transient metabolite produced by bifidobacteria and lactic bacteria which is converted into other organic acids by different bacterial species present in the gut. This explains the absence of this compound at the end of fermentation (Hughes, Shewry, Gibson, McCleary, & Rastall, 2008). As regards the formic acid, its highest concentrations were achieved after 24 h, although statistical differences were not observed between the employment of FOS or the refined oligosaccharides.

High concentrations of acetate were detected after 24 h of fermentation, being the levels significantly higher for the medium containing the refined oligosaccharides ($p \leq 0.05$). After 48 h of incubation, the concentration of the produced acetate in this medium reached a value of 87.46 mM, what supposed an increase of 30% with respect to the experiments in which FOS were used. The amount of acetate obtained in this work is higher than the reported in the fermentation of xylooligosaccharides from corn stover (Buruiana et al., 2017). Some studies have linked the production of acetate to different intestinal functions, including an increase of the colonic blood flow, an enhancement of the ideal motility, the regulation of the normal epithelial cell division, and it also plays an important role in the protection against genotoxic agents (Sharma & Shukla, 2016; Zheng, Lazarova, & Bordonaro, 2014).

Taking into account the propionate production, experiments containing the refined oligosaccharides gave rise to a significantly higher concentration of this acid (23.60 mM and 26.23 mM) after 24 and 48 h than when the medium made with FOS was used (12.09 mM and 13.2 mM, respectively). The concentration of propionate obtained in the present investigation is much higher than the observed by Gullón et al. (2014) when they evaluated the prebiotic effect of refined arabinoxyloligosaccharides from wheat bren (7.7-14.9 mM). During the same period, lower amount of butyrate (≈ 14 mM) was produced when both substrates were used. Multiple beneficial effects on the human health are associated with the production of propionate and butyrate from prebiotic carbohydrates. Propionate plays an important role in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases since it reduces lipogenesis and serum cholesterol level (Hosseini, Grootaert, Verstraete, & Van de Wiele, 2011). Butyrate acts as an anti-inflammatory agent and it is considered the preferred carbon source for the colonocytes (Zheng et al., 2014). Furthermore, numerous studies highlight the role of both acids in the prevention and in the inhibition of colorectal cancer (Canani et al., 2011; Jan et al., 2022; Sharma & Shukla, 2016).

The acetate/propionate ratio has been considered as an indicator of the potential hypolipidemic properties of the prebiotics, since it is associated with the reduction of liver lipid and cholesterol synthesis (den Besten et al., 2013). In this work, the values of this ratio at 48 h were 3.33 for the refined oligosaccharides and 4.67 for FOS. Buruiana et al. (2017) obtained an acetate/propionate ratio of 2.85 for purified xylooligosaccharides.

Overall, the profile of SCFAs obtained in this work was similar to what it has been reported in previous studies in which XOS with different structural characteristics were used (Ho et al., 2018; Ruíz et al., 2017).

Table 4. Mean value of organic acids concentration (mM) and pH of fermentation media made with XOS or FOS as carbon sources.

Carbon source	Time (h)	pH						
		pH	Lactate	Formiate	Acetate	Propionate	Butyrate	Total SCFA
XOS	0	7.2 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	2.02 (0.25) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	2.79 (1.44) ^a
	4	6.9(0.01)	0.11 (0.14) ^a	1.09 (0.12) ^a	2.19 (1.39) ^a	0.77 (1.33) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	9.95 (2.41) ^b
	10	6.5 (0.01)	4.50 (0.56) ^b	9.22 (2.48) ^b	38.17 (2.32) ^b	6.68 (0.99) ^b	1.11 (0.35) ^a	72.10 (7.23) ^b
	24	5.0 (0.01)	1.52 (0.87) ^a	13.14 (4.26) ^b	81.71 (2.99) ^c	23.60 (4.32) ^c	10.31 (1.10) ^{a,b}	131.39 (3.85) ^c
	48	4.8 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	11.78 (5.61) ^b	87.46 (3.69) ^c	26.23 (2.67) ^c	13.95 (3.30) ^a	139.43 (2.47) ^c
FOS	0	7.2 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	1.27 (0.47) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	2.15 (0.66) ^a
	4	6.89 (0.07)	2.52 (0.73) ^b	2.23(0.99) ^b	11.82 (3.70) ^b	0.88 (0.39) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	19.62 (2.21) ^c
	10	6.32 (0.08)	9.33 (2.52) ^c	10.23(1.93) ^b	34.98 (2.43) ^b	5.56 (0.86) ^b	6.37 (1.06) ^b	63.66 (6.09) ^b
	24	4.63 (0.08)	8.07 (1.38) ^b	15.63(3.52) ^b	60.98 (3.71) ^b	12.09 (2.46) ^b	14.67 (2.62) ^b	104.40 (2.07) ^b
	48	4.63 (0.04)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	13.91(3.23) ^b	61.30 (2.67) ^b	13.12 (1.11) ^b	14.24 (0.85) ^a	102.56 (5.24) ^b
Control	0	7.2 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	1.06 (0.62) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	1.06 (0.62) ^a
	4	7.26 (0.05)	0.08 (0.09) ^a	0.06 (0.06) ^a	0.74 (0.21) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.81 (0.19) ^a
	10	7.12 (0.08)	0.13 (0.11) ^a	2.96 (2.96) ^a	6.58 (0.98) ^a	2.28 (0.19) ^a	0.62 (0.23) ^a	12.45 (0.47) ^a
	24	6.86 (0.09)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.83 (0.83) ^a	23.07 (2.50) ^a	4.26 (1.12) ^a	5.70 (1.81) ^a	33.87 (4.26) ^a
	48	6.86 (0.10)	0.00 (0.00) ^a	0.00 (0.00) ^a	37.01 (5.67) ^a	7.40 (2.37) ^a	8.12 (2.69) ^a	52.52 (1.76) ^a

Starting concentration of the XOS and FOS were 1% (w/v). Data are presented as mean ± SD of three different donors. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for the same acid. Substrates were compared for all points of fermentation.

3.4.3. Refined oligosaccharides consumption

With regard to the assimilation of the oligosaccharide mixture it has been observed their almost total metabolization at the end of the fermentation. During the first 10 h of incubation, the oligosaccharide mixture was slowly assimilated by the intestinal microbiota and only 35% of the initial oligosaccharides was consumed. After 24 h of fermentation the concentration of XOS dropped markedly, being more than 80% of them consumed. The degree of OS consumption was consistent with the concentration profiles determined for the SCFA (see Table 4). The presence of substituents such as acetyl groups and methylated-glucuronic acid in the XOS may be the reason why this consumption pattern was sustained over time. A similar trend of this consumption pattern has been reported in other studies in which different oligosaccharides were used (Ho et al., 2018; Moniz et al., 2016). These results suggest that the XOS evaluated in the present study could reach (at least, in part) and exert their beneficial effects on the more distal colon, where there are increased risks of colon cancer and ulcerative colitis (Gullón et al., 2013).

3.4.4. Dynamics of the bifidobacterium population

The *Bifidobacterium* population was measured by analysing the pellets obtained after the prebiotic activity assessment by FISH, being the bifidogenic potential of the XOS shown in the Fig. 6. It has been demonstrated recently that the gut microbiome plays a key role in establishing and protecting the gastrointestinal health, and specifically the selective stimulation of bifidobacteria is overriding in this homeostasis process (Ruíz et al., 2017). When FOS or XOS were used the increase of the *Bifidobacterium* population was similar for the two analyzed time points ($p>0.05$). After 24 h of fermentation an increase of 14% (as average) was observed when the XOS and the FOS were used as substrates. These results were consistent with what it has been reported in the literature about the growth of *Bifidobacterium* using AXOS from wheat bran (Gullón et al., 2014) or XOS from corn stover (Buruiana et al., 2017).

Fig. 6. Variations (with respect to time 0 h) in Bifidobacterium population at 10 h and 24 h of incubation. The results are expressed as the average of the three donors. The initial bacterial counts was $7.93 \pm (0.15)$. Error bars indicate standard deviations ($n = 3$).

4. Conclusions

Vine shoots were hydrothermally treated under non-isothermal conditions at 200°C obtaining 0.588 kg/kg NVC of substituted oligosaccharides in the liquors. To increase the purity of these compounds, the liquors were subjected to a sequential processing of nanofiltration in concentration-diafiltration-concentration mode followed by an ion exchange process. The target compounds in refined mixture accounted for 0.977 kg target compounds/ kg NVC. For the first time, a depth structural characterization of the oligosaccharides obtained from a hydrothermal treatment of vine shoots was carried out. The FTIR showed the main characteristic bands of hemicellulosic oligosaccharides. The HPAEC-PAD allowed to elucidate the presence of oligosaccharides with DP in the range 2-6 and other complex oligosaccharides. The MALDI-TOF and UPLC-DAD-ESI-MS confirmed that the major compounds appertained at different oligosaccharide series constituted by a backbone of pentose and with different substituents such as hexoses, other pentoses, acetyl groups and methylhexuronic and hexuronic acids with DP until 18. By subjecting the oligosaccharides mixture to an *in vitro* fermentability with human faecal, it was observed that 80% of the oligosaccharides were consumed while short chain fatty acids, such as, acetate, propionate and butyrate together with the formiate were generated (accounting 139.4 mM) after 48 h of fermentation. Moreover, the bifidobacteria dynamic was monitored by FISH showing an increase of 14% of this target group using the oligosaccharides

mixture as substrate. These results confirmed the suitability of the refined mixture for its use as prebiotic ingredient.

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